

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF (*E*)-1,2-BIS(ALKYLTHIO AND ALKYL SULPHONYL)STILBENES*

R	Compd. no.	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Compd. no.	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂	1a	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ S ₂	86	77	2a	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ S ₂ O ₄	242	62
(CH ₂) ₃ OH	1b	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ S ₂	169	64	2b	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ S ₂ O ₄	277	78
CH ₂ (OH) ₂	1c	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ S ₂	96	59	2c	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ S ₂ O ₄	237	70
(OH) ₂ CHCH ₂	1d	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ S ₂	86	54	2d	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ S ₂ O ₄	274	58
CH ₂ (OH) ₂	1e	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ S ₂	51	56	2e	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ S ₂ O ₄	220	75
(OH) ₂ CH(OH) ₂	1f	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ S ₂	110	50	2f	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ S ₂ O ₄	224	76

*All compounds furnished satisfactory C and H analyses.

Similarly, other compounds (1b–f) were prepared (Table 1).

(*E*)-1,2-Bis(alkylsulphonyl)stilbenes (2). (*E*)-1,2-Bis(*n*-propylsulphonyl)stilbene: A mixture of (*E*)-1,2-bis(*n*-propylthio)stilbene (656 mg, 2 mmol) in acetic acid (50 ml) and 30% H₂O₂ (15 ml) was refluxed for 1 h and cooled. The solid separated was filtered and recrystallised from acetic acid (0.54 g, 70%), m.p. 242° (Found: C, 61.36; H, 6.34. C₂₀H₂₄S₂O₄ requires: C, 61.22; H, 6.12%); λ_{max} 243 (ε 13 420), 226 (19 530) and 230 nm (20 810); ν_{max} 1 144 (SO₂), 1 220 (C–S) and 1 325 cm⁻¹ (SO₂).

Similarly, other bis-sulphones (2b–f) were prepared (Table 1).

The yields of (*E*)-1,2-bis(alkylthio)stilbenes were fairly good. This may be attributed to the higher nucleophilicity of aliphatic thiols as compared to aromatic thiols.

The (*E*)-1,2-bis(alkylthio)stilbenes (1a–f) exhibited a conjugation band around 305–310 nm region (ε_{max} 6 180–7 977). This band seems to be due to the conjugation of the sulphide groups with stilbene nucleus. In (*E*)-1,2-bis(alkylsulphonyl)stilbenes (2a–f), the conjugation band occurred around 243–245 nm (ε_{max} 13 420–14 650). The hypsochromic and hypochromic shifts of conjugation band observed in 1,2-bis(alkylsulphonyl)stilbenes may be attributed to steric effects of SO₂-groups which prevent the molecule from assuming a planar configuration. Similar optical properties were observed in *trans*-1,2-dihalo-substituted-stilbenes¹⁰.

In the ir region, besides aromatic bands, no C=C stretching frequency was observed in both bis-sulphides and bis-sulphones. This may be attributed to the symmetry of the *trans*-(*E*) compounds. The ir spectra of bis-sulphones showed characteristic bands at 1 144 (SO₂), 1 220 (C–S) and 1 325 cm⁻¹ (SO₂).

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A New Facile Synthesis of Uridyl- (5'-3')-adenosine

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PROTECTING groups have been used for the synthesis of complex organic molecules by masking the sensitive groups in the molecule. Usual concept of protecting groups has been used only as 'masking' of the functional groups. A large number of activatable protecting groups¹ have been used for the synthesis of different oligonucleotides.

Nucleotide analogues have been very useful in the study of molecular biology. Synthetic oligonucleotides are being used for studying the mechanism of enzymatic actions on DNA *in vitro*² and elucidation of the genetic code³. Recently, several segments of DNA and RNA possessing interesting biological activities have been chemically synthesised⁴. Several analogues of purine-pyrimidine bases, nucleosides and nucleotides have proved very good antibiotics, anticancer and antiviral agents⁵. The chemical synthesis of a dinucleotide involves the joining of a nucleotide unit with another nucleoside through a phosphodiester linkage. Phosphodiester⁶ and phosphotriester⁷ are two methods of choice used

for the synthesis of oligonucleotides. Dimethyl phosphinothioyl group⁸ and diphenyl phosphinothioyl group⁹ have already been used for the synthesis of nucleotides in 70–90% yields.

Experimental

Paper chromatography was carried out by the descending technique on Whatman no. 1 paper and tlc on silica gel G plates. Solvent 'C' refers to isopropanol–NH₃–H₂O (7 : 1 : 2, v/v). The uv spectra were taken on a Shimadzu 260 spectrophotometer and ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer. Phosphorus containing compounds were detected on a chromatogram after spraying with Ischerwood reagent¹⁰ and exposing them to uv-lamp¹¹. Thiophosphoryl tribromide¹² and dialkylphosphinothioyl bromide¹³ were prepared by the reported methods.

2',3',5'-O-Tris-diethylphosphinothioyluridine (3a) : Uridine (2 ; 0.5 mmol) was added to a solution of diethylphosphinothioyl bromide (1a ; 1.75 mmol) in pyridine (1.5 ml) and the reaction mixture stirred at 5° for 4 h. Ice-cold water (10 ml) was then added to the reaction mixture and extracted with chloroform. Tlc on silica gel (CHCl₃–MeOH, 9 : 1, v/v) indicated four spots. The spot having R_f=0.64 was eluted with chloroform–methanol mixture (10 : 1) and characterised as 2',3',5'-O-tris-diethylphosphinothioyluridine (3a ; 78%) (Found : C, 41.68 ; H, 6.43 ; N, 4.61. C₃₁H₅₉O₆N₂P₃S₃ requires : C, 41.72 ; H, 6.45 ; N, 4.63%) ; λ_{max} 260 nm ; ν_{max} 1700 (C=O), 1230 (P–O) and 715 cm⁻¹ (P=S).

2',3'-O-Bis-diethylphosphinothioyluridylyl-(5'-3')-adenosine (5a) : Adenosine-3'-phosphate (4 ; 0.125 mmol) and silver acetate (0.125 mmol) were taken in pyridine (2 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. 2',3',5'-O-Tris-diethylphosphinothioyluridine (0.025 mmol) was then added all at once. The reaction mixture was stirred for 24 h in dark at room temperature and then H₂S was passed through the solution and the resulting black precipitate was removed by centrifuging. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure and applied on preparative tlc using solvent 'C'. Three spots were detected on the plate. The spot having R_f=0.52 was identified as the title compound 5a (58%) (Found : C, 39.82 ; H, 5.15 ; N, 12.04. C₃₇H₆₃O₁₂N₇P₃S₃ requires : C, 39.85 ; H, 5.16 ; N, 12.05%) ; λ_{max} (pH 7) 265 nm ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3350 (OH), 3200, 1600, 1180, 805 (C–NH₂), 1235 (P–O) and 715 cm⁻¹ (P=S).

Uridylyl-(5'-3')-adenosine (6) : 5a (10 mg) was dissolved in half-saturated methanolic ammonia (1.5 ml, 0°) and the solution stirred for 48 h at room temperature. It was then filtered and washed with dilute ammonia. Careful evaporation of the filtrate and washings under reduced pressure removed ammonia and methanol to yield the title compound (6 ; 50%) ; R_f=0.45 (pc, solvent 'C') ; λ_{max} (pH 7) 260 nm ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3370 (OH), 3200,

1608, 1180, 805 (C–NH₂), 1235 (P–O) and 1573 cm⁻¹ (C=O). Superimposable ir spectra, co-pc and co-tlc with authentic sample⁹ confirmed the identity of compound 6.

2',3',5'-O-Tris-di-n-propylphosphinothioyluridine (3b) : Uridine (2 ; 0.5 mmol) was added to a solution of di-n-propylphosphinothioylbromide (1b ; 1.75 mmol) in pyridine (1.5 ml) and the reaction mixture was stirred at 5° for 4 h. The pure product having R_f=0.61 was obtained in 82% yield and chromatographically purified (Found : C, 47.05 ; H, 7.40 ; N, 4.02. C₃₇H₆₁O₆N₂P₃S₃ requires : C, 47.09 ; H, 7.41 ; N, 4.06%) ; λ_{max} (pH 7) 260 nm ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1710 (C=O), 1230 (P–O) and 715 cm⁻¹ (P=S).

2',3'-O-Bis-di-n-propylphosphinothioyluridylyl-(5'-3')-adenosine (5b) : Adenosine-3'-phosphate (4 ; 0.125 mmol) and silver acetate (0.125 mmol) were reacted with 3b (0.025 mmol) in pyridine (2 ml) with stirring for 24 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual. The product having R_f=0.50 (solvent 'C') was obtained in 65% yield (Found : C, 42.78 ; H, 5.76 ; N, 11.30. C₃₁H₅₀N₇P₃S₃O₁₂ requires : C, 42.80 ; H, 5.75 ; N, 11.27%) ; λ_{max} (pH 7) 264 nm ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3370 (OH), 3200, 1608, 1180, 805 (C–NH₂), 1230 (P–O) and 715 cm⁻¹ (P=S).

Hydrolysis with methanolic ammonia afforded uridylyl-(5'-3')-adenosine in 55% yield.

2',3',5'-O-Tris-di-n-butylphosphinothioyluridine (3c) : Uridine (2 ; 0.25 mmol) was reacted with di-n-butylphosphinothioyl bromide (1c ; 0.875 mmol) in pyridine (1.5 ml) to give the title compound 3c having R_f=0.60 (CHCl₃–MeOH, 9 : 1, v/v) in 80% yield and chromatographically purified (Found : C, 51.28 ; H, 8.15 ; N, 3.60. C₄₃H₈₃O₆N₂P₃S₃ requires : C, 51.29 ; H, 8.16 ; N, 3.62%) ; λ_{max} (pH 7) 260 nm ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1710 (C=O), 1230 (P–O) and 715 cm⁻¹ (P=S).

2',3'-O-Bis-di-n-butylphosphinothioyluridylyl-(5'-3')-adenosine (5c) : Adenosine-3'-phosphate (4 ; 0.125 mmol) and silver acetate (0.125 mmol) were dissolved in pyridine (2 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 30 min. Compound 3c (0.025 mmol) was then added all at once. The reaction mixture was further stirred for 24 h at room temperature. The completion of the reaction was monitored by tlc on silica gel G plates. The product having R_f=0.46 was obtained in 60% yield (Found : C, 45.40 ; H, 6.25 ; N, 10.57. C₃₅H₆₅O₁₂N₇P₃S₃ requires : C, 45.40 ; H, 6.27 ; N, 10.59%) ; λ_{max} (pH 7) 264 nm ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3370 (OH), 3200, 1600, 1180, 805 (C–NH₂), 1230 (P–O) and 715 cm⁻¹ (P=S).

Compound 5c on hydrolysis with methanolic ammonia gave uridylyl-(5'-3')-adenosine in 52% yield.

Results and Discussion

In this paper the use of dialkylphosphinothioyl-bromides (1 ; alkyl=ethyl, n-propyl, n-butyl) in

the synthesis of uridylyl-(5'-3')-adenosine (6) has been reported (Scheme 1). 5'-O-Dialkylphosphinothiouridine could not be prepared selectively in pure form by reacting uridine (2) with an equimolar

amount of dialkylphosphinothiobromide (1) under different reaction conditions but a mixture of mono-, di- and tri-substituted derivatives was obtained. The selective activation of the 5'-position of similar nucleoside triesters is known^{8,9}.

Uridine on reaction with dialkylphosphinothiobromide (1) in pyridine afforded 2',3',5'-O-tris-dialkylphosphinothiouridine (3a-c) in 78-82% yield. Alongwith this nucleoside triester, traces of monoester and diester were also detected in the reaction products by chromatography. The elemental analysis and ir spectra were in conformity with the structure. 2',3',5'-O-Tris-dialkylphosphinothiouridine (3a-c) when reacted with adenosine 3'-phosphate (4) in pyridine in the presence of silver acetate gave 2',3'-O-bis-dialkylphosphinothiouridylyl-(5'-3')-adenosine (5a-c) in 50-65% yield. 2',3'-O-Bis-dialkylphosphinothiouridylyl-(5'-3')-adenosine (5a-c) on hydrolysis with methanolic ammonia afforded uridylyl-(5'-3')-adenosine (6) in 50-55% yield. The structure was confirmed on the basis of its uv, ir, elemental analysis, co-tlc and co-pc with the authentic sample.

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Synthesis of 3-Substituted-aminopropoxy-2'-hydroxycoumarin Derivatives as Possible β -Blockers

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PROPRANOLOL, a well-known β -adrenergic blocking drug, was first introduced for the treatment of angina and later found to possess significant anti-hypertensive activity¹. It is therefore hoped that the compounds 3, prepared by attaching β -blocking sidechain to 7-position of coumarin ring system may